

D3.14. Report on the recently started projects – 2nd call

Workpackage 3

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Contributing partners: SSI, SVA, INSA, UoS, BfR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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D3.14. REPORT ON THE RECENTLY STARTED PROJECTS – 2ND CALL

Introduction

In the ‘Guidelines for project leaders to report on JRP’ (D3.1) and the ‘Instructions for monitoring of and reporting on JIPs’ (D4.1) a first reporting quickly after the start of the projects is mentioned. This document summarizes the results of the second online questionnaire that was sent out to the leaders of projects that were to start in January 2020 (13 JRP and 3 JIP). The survey was set up in Microsoft Forms and managed by SVA, Sweden.

The objective of this reporting activity was to obtain practical information about specific issues of the projects. Also, it is considered useful to build and maintain a productive relationship between the One Health EJP management, particularly but not only, WP3 and WP4 leaders, and the project leaders.

The questionnaire is included as an annex. For some of the questions, project leaders were invited to write comments as free text, but this was voluntary.

In this report, all questions and their answers are summarized. Some comments are quoted, and if judged necessary, typing errors were corrected. Names of projects and institutions and other elements in the comments that could lead to the identification of the author were anonymized.

1. Participation

The One Health EJP WP3 team invited project leaders to take part in the online questionnaire on 25th of February 2020; a reminder was sent on 16th of March. On the 2nd of June those project leaders that had not replied yet were contacted individually. All JRP and JIP answered between the 25th of February and the 29th of June 2020.

Start of the projects and date of kick-off meetings

All projects started in January 2020. Six projects had their kick-off meeting in January 2020, five in February, and one in April. One project had a TC kick-off on the 9th of January and had planned to have a physical meeting during a congress in March, but that was cancelled due to COVID-19 pandemic.

Recruitment of personnel

During the joint kick-off meeting of the second call projects, organised by the Project Management Team in Berlin on 13th of November 2019, the project leaders of the second call projects were encouraged to launch the recruitment process for project collaborators. The survey responses showed that much of the recruitment was on-going or completed, but not all. Project leaders often referred to the COVID-19 crisis to explain the delay in the hiring process. Some project leaders were not aware of any recruitment, nor whether the process was finished.

2. Data management plan (DMP)

Among other occasions, it was mentioned at the kick-off meeting in Berlin (13th of November 2019) that each project would have to develop a specific data management plan.

Fifteen of the 16 respondents had informed their consortium members of this mandatory task, and 12 had already assigned this task to somebody in the project consortium.

3. Communication and dissemination activities

Communication and dissemination activities are strategically important for the promotion of the One Health EJP and its outcome, and to gain impact among partner institutes and all stakeholders, including the media and the public.

Twelve of the 16 projects planned **to develop a communication plan** for their project. The communication media that were mentioned were the website of the project leader's institution, social media like Twitter and LinkedIn (10 respondents) and channels familiar to scientists (congresses, publications, posters).

The questions seemed to raise awareness among project leaders and some of them planned to contact the One Health EJP Communication Team at Surrey.

Thirteen of the 16 project leaders are aware of **the dissemination procedure** that has been developed by the One Health EJP and that is available on its website. One respondent noted that the document has been discussed during the project kick-off meeting.

When asked **how the communication team could support project leaders** in their communication and dissemination efforts, several suggestions were proposed and various levels of expectation were formulated, such as the drafting of transparent and simple guidelines (including one on the communication to the general public), the suggestion to publish short and catchy news on the projects, to help with social media, website and newsletters, the need to inform stakeholders about the projects' progress and to disseminate results.

All project leaders were aware of **the One Health EJP scientific publication policy** that can be found on its website. Some respondents mentioned that the policy was discussed during their kick-off meeting.

Half of the projects leaders indicated they knew that on the One Health EJP website an **online tool** to gather information on **participation at conferences and events**. For some it is not clear when it should be used (when organising an event or other effort in the context of the One Health EJP, or when taking part in external conferences where the EJP is presented). Another respondent wanted to know if this database could be consulted (which is not the case: it is only published once a year in the Periodic Report). One project leader mentioned that the link was communicated during the projects' kick-off meeting.

Only three of the projects replied to have plans **to organize a conference** where a broader audience can attend. More information can be found in the project proposals.

4. Internal and external contacts

All project leaders were aware that **the One Health EJP website provides private spaces** (so-called **groups**) for all projects and they have informed their consortium members about this. Some project leaders mentioned that the One Health EJP web space is useful, while some indicated finding it less user-friendly.

When asking about **the Horizon 2020 requirement concerning ethics matters** and referring to the ethics self-assessment, fourteen project leaders confirmed that their consortium members were well informed and that they are taking the necessary measures according to the local (regional, national) legislation. Some respondents commented that they will disseminate the information and make sure to implement the requirements.

The grant agreement of the One Health EJP foresees (but does not require) the set-up of **national mirror groups** consisting of professionals from line ministries or agencies that deal with foodborne zoonoses, AMR and emerging threats. About half of the project leaders were aware that such mirror groups exist, but have few information about them.

Project leaders were asked if they were supportive of having **regular formal and informal contact with the One Health EJP WP3 and WP4 teams**. While most respondents supported a good relationship with WP3 and WP4, some suggested that email contact is sufficient and others proposed participation of WP collaborators at TC or meetings. Finally, some project leaders did not see any advantage in close collaborations.

Project leaders were asked about **the relevance of a direct contact with international stakeholders** (ECDC and EFSA) to their project and if they have suggestions or ideas for how the One Health EJP could help in this regard. The comments demonstrated that many project leaders see a noticeable advantage in contacting and meeting with ECDC or EFSA, and that some already have worked on this relationship. Other project leaders seemed to be more reluctant.

5. Identification of relevant contacts

Related to the question of installing favoured contacts with ECDC and EFSA, contacts with members of the Scientific Steering Board (SSB), with the General Director of the partner organizations (the Project Management Committee, PMC), and with national stakeholders (Programme Owners Committee, POC: representatives of Ministries of Public Health, Agriculture, Research etc.) was questioned.

When asked about their most relevant contacts, 13 project leaders chose SSB, either as first or second choice.

Finally, project leaders were invited to express **any suggestion or remark** that they want to share with the One Health EJP Project Management Team. Suggestions included need for information on other international One Health initiatives, for cross-project discussions and a specific remark regarding databases for large nucleotide sequences.

Conclusion of the survey

Despite the challenging conditions during which the online survey was organised (COVID-19 pandemic), the information gathered is of precious value to the One Health EJP Project Management Team and One Health EJP Communications Team. The results confirmed the projects had started as planned, indicated good information flow of relevant aspects, and provided constructive feedback that can inform further support activities.

The survey outcome demonstrated that project leaders were well informed about the need for a Data Management Plan, and that they had taken action to fulfil this obligation.

There seemed to be a need for support concerning the communication and dissemination of the outcomes of the projects: both the Communications Team and the WP on Science to policy are aware of these issues and will help project leaders with these activities as they are very important for gaining impact. Some practical suggestions and expectations were put forward and will be addressed in due course.

The survey also highlighted the need to bring project leaders into contact with the international stakeholders, not only ECDC and EFSA but also with those organisations that joined the Stakeholders Committee in the spring of 2020, i.e. EEA, EMA, FAO, WHO-EU and OIE. The One Health EJP WP on Science to policy will pay special attention to this.

As for the mirror groups that are ongoing in the various countries, it is at the moment unfortunately not possible to better inform project leaders, as this information is far from complete.

Many project leaders noted that their relevant contacts regarding their project are the SSB members. The Coordination Team will put this point on the agenda of a following SSB meeting. A good contact between researchers and the local management is a prerequisite for the efficient transfer of scientific

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and integrative information and will lead to efficient implementation of newly developed procedures, methodologues, capacities etc., also beyond the end of the One Health EJP.

Finally, the project leaders made useful suggestions to the One Health EJP management that may support their collaboration.

Annex

Questionnaire for the recently started projects -2nd call

Participation

1. Is your project a JRP or JIP?

Dropdown list: JRP; JIP

2. Name of JRP

Dropdown list: ADONIS; BEONE; BIOPIGEE; DISCOVER; FARMED; FED-AMR; FULL-FORCE; IDEMBRU; MEME; PARADISE; TELE-Vir; TOXOSOURCES; WORLDCOM

3. Name of JIP

Dropdown list: CARE; MATRIX; OH-HARMONY-CAP

4. Your name

Enter your answer

5. Your function

Dropdown list: Project leader; Project deputy leader

6. Your project was planned to start in January 2020. What was the actual start date?

Enter your answer

7. If you or any of your partners plan to recruit staff to the project, what is the actual status of this recruitment?

Enter your answer

8. When did/will you have your project's kick-off meeting?

Enter your answer

Data management plan (DMP)

As mentioned at the kick-off meeting in Berlin, each project will develop a specific data management plan.

9. Have you informed the members of your project consortium about this?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

10. Comments to above

Enter your answer

11. Have you already assigned this task to somebody in your project consortium?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

12. Comments to above

Enter your answer

Communication and dissemination activities

The European Commission emphasises the importance of the communication and dissemination activities.

Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about the action and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public.

Dissemination is the disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications, in any medium.

A One Health EJP communication strategy, including a communication network, website, newsletters and press releases, etc. has been developed and social media are frequently used for external communication.

13. Have you, or do you plan to develop a communication plan for your own project?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

14. Comments to above

Enter your answer

15. Do you plan to use social media to communicate on activities and results related to your project?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

16. Comments to above

Enter your answer

17. The PMT and Comms team will, with your input and approval, promote your project outputs within and outside the OHEJP consortium through the official channels (newsletters, contacts with REA and its steering group, specific communications, etc.). The project outcomes flow is described in the dissemination procedure that can be found on the website (<https://onehealthejp.eu/groups/key-project-documents/projects/59/files>). Are you aware of this document?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

18. Comments to above

Enter your answer

19. How can the communication team support you in your communication and dissemination efforts?

Enter your answer

20. The OHEJP Scientific Publication Policy (<https://onehealthejp.eu/groups/key-project-documents/projects/59/file>) purpose is to guarantee that the scientific outputs using a peer-review process, generated from the OHEJP, are published to the maximum possible scientific standards, using a coordinated and appropriate approach. Are you aware of this publication policy?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

21. Comments to above

Enter your answer

22. Conferences and events constitute an important aspect of the dissemination of OHEJP outcomes. On the One Health EJP website a tool is available (<https://onehealthejp.eu/internal-events-survey/>) to register OHEJP dissemination activities and events. Are you aware that every dissemination activity must be registered on the website as indicated above?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

23. Comments to above

Enter your answer

24. Do you plan to organize conferences where a broader audience can attend?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

25. Comments to above

Enter your answer

Internal and external contacts

26. The One Health EJP website provides private spaces (groups) for all projects. Have you informed your consortium members about this?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

27. Comments to above

Enter your answer

28. Together with your project proposal, a self-assessment on ethical issues was submitted. Do you confirm that all partners in the JRP / JIP consortium are well informed and that they are taking the necessary measures according to the local (regional, national) legislation?

Dropdown list: Yes; No

29. Comments to above

Enter your answer

30. As defined in the grant agreement, national mirror groups consisting of professionals from line ministries or agencies that deal with foodborne zoonoses, AMR and emerging threats may be set up. These groups can give valuable input to One Health EJP and its projects, and efficiently disseminate the outcome of the One Health EJP to risk managers and other appropriate stakeholders. Are you aware of mirror groups in the countries of your consortium?

Enter your answer

31. WP3 and WP4 leaders and deputy leaders are convinced that regular formal and informal contact with you and your project is important. Do you have suggestions or ideas for the contact with the WP3 and WP4?

Enter your answer

32. WP5 of OHEJP focuses on Science to Policy translation and has established contacts with international stakeholders, including ECDC and EFSA. What are your thoughts about the relevance of a direct contact with international stakeholders to your project? Do you have suggestions or ideas for how WP5 could help your project in this regard?

Enter your answer

Identification of relevant contacts

Contacts with members of SSB (Scientific Steering Board, Scientific Director, Head of department or similar), PMC (Program Managers Committee, General Director of your organization, CEO) and POC (Program Owners Committee, representatives of Ministries of Public Health, Agriculture, Research etc. and/or of Food Agency) are very useful to present the outcome of your project to the decision makers and risk managers. Contacts may consist of formal or informal meetings, gatherings and even calls, and facilitate spreading information and having long lasting impact.

Who would you identify as the first and second most relevant contact?

33. Most relevant contact

Dropdown list: SSB; PMC; POC

34. Second most relevant contact

Dropdown list: SSB; PMC; POC

35. How do you plan to interact with these stakeholders?

Enter your answer

36. Finally, do you have other general suggestions or remarks you want to share with the Project Management Team (PMT)?

Enter your answer

Submit the survey.